

Underground Corrosion of Metals and Alloys. Part III

K. Roy, M. Sarkar, and B. Chatterjee

While pitting under field exposure has been observed to be many times greater than that occurs in the corrosion cell for a particular combination of soil and ferrous material, the electrode in the corrosion cell suffers a much higher weight loss compared to that found under the field conditions. The difference in the physical and chemical characteristics of soils of four major Indian soil groups does not seem to be reflected in the corrosivity of the latter for cast iron and mild steel.

In continuation of our work^{1,2} on the underground corrosion of metals and alloys using electrolytic corrosion cell³⁻⁸, studies have been made on corrosion under field conditions of cast iron (C.I.) (C, 3.1%; Mn, 0.91%; Si, 2.09%; P, 0.27%; S, 0.12%), mild steel (M. S.) (C, 0.28%; Mn, 0.91%; Si, 0.08%; P, 0.03%; S, 0.04%), carbon steel (C. S.) (C, 0.43%; Si, 0.12%; Mn, 0.66%; S, 0.013%; P, 0.015%), and a steel containing a small amount of nickel (N. S.) (C, 0.17%; Si, 0.01; Mn, 0.93%; Ni, 0.10%; S, 0.013%; P, 0.025%) at selected spots on the Durgapur-Calcutta route, viz., Burdwan, Saktigarh, and Chinsurah. For this purpose, specimens made from the above materials were kept buried under the soil at a depth of 2 ft. The protective action of anticorrosive red-lead paint on underground corrosion under field conditions has also been studied. The results of the investigation on the underground corrosion of the above specimens under field condition have been compared in Table I with those obtained in the laboratory, using corrosion cell and the particular combination of soil and electrode material. The corrosivity of four major groups of Indian soils for cast iron and mild steel has also been studied using corrosion cells.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples were taken out from the soil after one year, treated with a 10% solution of ammonium citrate, made alkaline with ammonia to remove the corrosion products, and finally the losses in weight of the specimens as also the extent of pitting in the samples were determined. The details of the experimental set-up used for the laboratory tests

1. Chatterjee and Gupta, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1959, 22, 159.
2. Roy *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, 24, 113.
3. Denison and Ewing, *Soil Sci.*, 1935, 40, 287.
4. Denison, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Std.*, U.S.A., 1936, 17, 363.
5. Denison and Romanoff, *Corrosion*, 1953, 9, 141.
6. Schwerdtfeger and McDorman, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1952, 99, 407.
7. Schwerdtfeger, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Std.*, U.S.A., 1953, 50, 329.
8. Schwerdtfeger and McDorman, *Corrosion*, 1952, 8, 391.

using corrosion cells and the methods used for the determination of the physical, chemical, and electrochemical characteristics of the soils were the same as reported in previous publications^{1,2}.

TABLE I

Underground corrosion of ferrous materials.

Locality.	Test specimen.	Wt. loss in g./cm ² of		Max. pitting (mils).		Samples coated with anticorrosive paint.	
		cathode & anode in corrosion cell.	sample under field condition.	Corrosion cell.	Under field exposure.	Max. pitting (mils).	Wt. loss (g./cm ²).
Burdwan	C.I.	0.077	0.018	6.0	4	Nil	Nil
	M.S.	0.057	0.041	7.0	24	"	"
	C.S.	0.046	0.027	1.0	10	"	0.09
	N.S.	0.059	0.039	1.0	18	"	Nil
Saktigarh	C.I.	0.056	0.035	2.0	6	"	Nil
	M.S.	0.066	0.025	6.0	26	"	"
	C.S.	0.046	0.020	3.0	20	"	"
	N.S.	0.041	0.030	1.5	18	"	"
Chinsurah	C.I.	0.074	0.034	3.0	17	"	0.09
	M.S.	0.077	0.033	16.0	66	"	Nil
	C.S.	0.052	0.041	0.5	58	"	"
	N.S.	0.059	0.034	2.0	53	"	"

DISCUSSION

It appears from the above data that corrosivity under laboratory conditions, using corrosion cells, of the three soils for the four ferrous materials used does not appear to follow a regular order. The data also indicate clearly that the corrosivity of soils for metals and alloys is very specific and does not depend only on the soil characteristics and compositions of the materials exposed to soils.

Table I shows that pitting observed under field conditions is many times greater than that observed in the corrosion cell for a particular combination of soil and electrode material. It is rather interesting to note that whereas the pitting in the samples is many times more under field conditions compared to that observed in the corrosion cells, the combined weight losses of the electrodes, as observed in the latter case, are much higher compared to the former, *i.e.*, more pitting under field exposure but more weight losses in the corrosion cell. It is also observed that the specimens having a single coat of anticorrosive red-lead paint suffer practically no corrosion when exposed to the three soils used under field conditions for a period of one year.

Indian soils have been classified into four major groups, *viz.*, black, red, laterite, and alluvial, depending on their physical and chemical properties and genesis. It is therefore of interest to see if the difference in properties of these four groups of soils is also

TABLE II

Corrosivity of four major groups of Indian soils for cast iron and mild steel in relation to their physical and chemical characteristics.

Soils.	Clay.	pH.	Water-holding capacity.	Total water-soluble salt.	Anionic concentration of water extract (m.g./100 g. soil).	Material used.	Combined wt. losses of anode & cathode (g./cm ²).	Max. pitting (mils).	Initial cell current (μA).				
				CO ₃ ²⁻ , HCO ₃ , Cl, SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻									
Amraoti (black).	52.80%	8.00	08.41%	0.107%	0.14	0.07	0.20	0.10	0.10	C.I. M.S.	0.041 0.010	9 1	82 100
Bangalore (red)	41.00	6.95	30.31	0.060	Nil	0.51	0.10	0.38	0.10	C.I. M.S.	0.052 0.040	5 11	20 10
Benlure (laterite)	28.70	5.10	43.02	0.007	Nil	0.51	0.09	0.80	0.13	C.I. M.S.	0.053 0.050	5 8	10 10
Berhampur (alluvial)	23.36	6.72	52.62	0.183	0.21	2.04	0.34	0.48	0.27	C.I. M.S.	0.044 0.010	5 0.5	20 30

manifested in their corrosivity for metals and alloys. For this purpose, the corrosivity of Amraoti black cotton soil, Bangalore red soil, Bankura laterite soil, and Berhampur alluvial soil for cast iron and mild steel have been studied using Denison corrosion cells¹ modified by Schwerdtfeger and following the same procedure as already mentioned. The cells were dismantled after 6 months and the combined weight losses of cathode and anode and the maximum pitting on the electrodes were determined. The results obtained are recorded in Table II. The important physical and chemical characteristics of these soils have also been included in the table.

The weight losses of mild steel and cast iron electrodes with respect to Amraoti black soils and Berhampur alluvial soils are almost the same. Thus, the relative corrosivity of these two soils for the ferrous materials used appears to be almost identical though these differ widely in composition and physical characteristics (Table II). Mild steel in these two soils show greater resistance to corrosion compared to cast iron. Bangalore red soil and Bankura laterite soil are more corrosive with respect to both cast iron and mild steel compared to the other two soils. Mild steel in Bangalore soil suffers more corrosion compared to cast iron, whereas Bankura soil has almost the same corrosivity for both cast iron and mild steel. Both Bangalore and Bankura soils again exhibited almost identical corrosivity for cast iron in spite of their widely varying composition and physical characteristics. It is also evident from the data presented in Table II that combined weight losses of the anode and cathode and maximum pitting on the surface of the electrodes do not seem to bear any correlation with the initial cell current, the total soluble salt in the soils, the clay percentage, the water-holding capacity of the respective soils, or the individual constituent in the water extracts. Further work on the correlation between soil types and their corrosivity for metals and alloys is in progress and interpretation of the results obtained so far is deferred pending accumulation of further data.

The authors express their sincerest thanks to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Government of India, for financing this investigation.